

INTERFACE HEALING DURING THE PROCESSING OF REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

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ABSTRACT

The fusion bonding, or healing, of semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers is of considerable interest in novel manufacturing techniques using an integrated processing (IP) concept. The goal of this approach is to use high performance composites in combination with neat resin and engineering composites to make complex parts. In this work the healing between unidirectional fiber reinforced polypropylene (UD) and glass mat reinforced thermoplastic (GMT) is examined. The fracture energy of the bonds was characterized using wedge test and double cantilever beam fracture geometries. For all bonding combinations investigated, the fracture energy increased with increasing interface temperature. Furthermore, bonding between solid GMT and molten UD always produced higher fracture energies than bonding between molten GMT and solid UD.

INTRODUCTION

The fusion bonding, or healing, of semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers has been of considerable commercial interest: compression molding of advanced composite materials in the aerospace industry is one example; butt welding of polyolefin pipe is another. An area that has recently received more attention is integrated processing (IP) where materials with different reinforcing phases are combined using several different processes [1]. The essence of this approach is to use high performance materials of high intrinsic properties in combination with neat resin and easily shaped reinforced materials, to meet the performance and functional requirements of geometrically complex parts. The performance and economic advantages of such integration have been examined by Smith et al. [1]. Preliminary work focused on understanding the influence of processing conditions on the degree of bonding, or interface healing, of neat polypropylene adherends [2]. In this work the effect of the presence of a reinforcing phase on healing between glass fiber reinforced polypropylene composites is examined.

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EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION AND PREFORM CONSOLIDATION

The materials used in this work were polypropylene matrix/glass fiber composites. Two reinforcement configurations were examined; (1) an unpigmented glass mat thermoplastic (GMT) with a glass content of 28.4 wt % supplied by Symalit AG, and (2) a continuous unidirectional glass fiber prepreg tape (UD) with a glass content of 52.6 wt % purchased from Imperial Chemical Industries Ltd.

The GMT was received as sheet with a nominal thickness of 3.7 mm and cut into 50 mm by 50 mm plaques. The UD tape, 25 cm wide, had a nominal thickness of 0.5 mm. UD plaques were made by cutting 50 mm long strips from the UD tape and cutting three 50 mm wide pieces from the center of each strip. These were then placed in a square, 50 mm by 50 mm, matched-die mold, preheated to 200°C and consolidated under a pressure of 2 MPa. After 10 minutes at the selected temperature, cooling was initiated and the pressure maintained until the mold cooled to 25°C. The final thickness of a consolidated UD plaque was 1.4 mm. The flexural moduli of the GMT and the consolidated UD plaques were measured in 3-point bending. The span between load supports was 45 mm, the loading points were 5 mm diameter steel rods, and the crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/minute. The fiber volume fraction was determined by weighing a plaque before and after ashing in an oven at 600°C for 1 hour. The melting temperature of the matrix of each material was characterized using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7. Samples were heated at 10°C/min in nitrogen from 50°C to 200°C and the onset and peak melting temperatures recorded.

HEALING EXPERIMENTS

Non-isothermal bonds were made using an instrumented matched-die mold, shown in Figure 1, as done in previous experiments for neat polypropylene adherends [2]. The mold was cleaned with acetone prior to each bonding experiment. A plaque was attached to the upper mold with 5 mm and 15 mm wide strips of 28 μ m thick Kapton tape; the wider Kapton strip served as a crack initiator for fracture tests. The upper mold was set to temperature T_1 , below the melting point of the material, and varied between 110 and 160°C. The oven temperature was kept approximately 2°C below T_1 . The temperature of the lower mold, T_2 , was constant at 200°C. The heaters for the molds and oven were turned on and heated to the set temperatures. After heating the molds to the required temperature, a plaque was placed inside the lower mold and covered with an insulating sheet. The whole system was then allowed to equilibrate for time t_e after which the insulating sheet was removed and the mold closed to pressure p . After a hold time of 42 seconds, the heaters and oven were turned off and cooling initiated. The pressure was maintained until the mold cooled to 25°C. Four series of experiments were performed; the experimental parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Experimental Parameters

Series	upper plaque (solid)	lower plaque (melt)	t_e (minutes)	p (MPa)
1	UD	UD	10	2
2	GMT	GMT	15	5
3	GMT	UD	10	5
4	UD	GMT	15	5

For comparison, two isothermal bonds, $T_1=T_2$, were made in a square, 150 mm by 150 mm, picture frame mold under identical processing conditions. The bonds were a GMT/GMT bond and an eight ply UD specimen. A 50 mm wide strip of Kapton tape was used as a crack initiator midway through the specimen thickness. The mold was preheated to 200°C and an unconsolidated specimen placed in the mold. The mold was then closed so that mold faces just touched the specimen. After 10 minutes a pressure of 2.5 MPa was applied and cooling initiated. As for the other specimens, the pressure was maintained until the mold reached 25°C.

To compare the temperatures of the non-isothermal and isothermal bonds, the same criterion as in reference [2] is used. For the non-isothermal bonds, the temperature of the interface between the solid and molten plaques at the moment when they touch, before any melting or solidification has occurred, and neglecting differences in thermal diffusivity, will be the average temperature, \bar{T} , of the plaques, i.e.,

$$\bar{T} = \frac{1}{2}(T_1+T_2), \quad (1)$$

where T_1 and T_2 are the temperatures of the upper and lower plaques, respectively.

FRACTURE TESTING

Fracture specimens, 10 mm by 50 mm, were cut from the non-isothermally bonded specimens. The mode I fracture energy of the bonds was measured using a double cantilever beam (DCB) geometry with a constant crack opening displacement (COD) as shown in Figure 2a. Both edges of the specimens were viewed using two 45° prisms on either side of the specimen as shown in Figure 2b. Crack propagation was accomplished by forcing the specimens over a 0.45 mm thick razor blade in a screw driven load frame at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/minute. For Series 2 bonds made below $T_j = 140^\circ\text{C}$, a 0.29 mm wedge was used. Crack lengths were measured directly on a video monitor at 20X magnification at 2.5 mm intervals over a 10 mm length at the mid-point of the specimen. Minimum resolution was 0.2 mm. The average crack length from both sides of the specimen at each position was used in the calculation of G_{Ic} at that position.

The isothermal bonds were cut into 20 mm by 150 mm specimens and prepared for DCB testing in accordance with the EGF/ASTM protocol [3]. Crack propagation was accomplished by opening the crack at a constant rate of 2 mm/minutes and recording the load, P , as a function of displacement, Δ . The crack length was recorded as a function of displacement on the P - Δ plot.

The critical strain energy release rate of the Series 1 bonds was calculated using an equation derived by Kanninen [4] based on the bending of a prismatic beam supported by an elastic foundation. The key assumptions for the equation are: (i) the only contribution to the stored elastic energy of the system is from the bending of the free portions of the beams and the elastic deformation ahead of the crack tip, (ii) the elastic energy ahead of the crack tip is well described by an elastic foundation, and (iii) all the elastic energy released upon fracture is absorbed by plastic deformation at the crack tip [5]. For this case G_{Ic} , is given by

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3\Delta^2 E_1 h_1^3 E_2 h_2^3}{8a^4} \left(\frac{E_1 h_1^3 C_2^2 + E_2 h_2^3 C_1^2}{(E_1 h_1^3 C_2^3 + E_2 h_2^3 C_1^3)^2} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $C_1=1+0.64h_1/a$, $C_2=1+0.64h_2/a$, Δ is the wedge thickness, E is the elastic modulus, h is the beam thicknesses, a is the crack length, and the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the upper and

lower beams, respectively. This equation is only valid if the crack propagates along the interface. If the beams are symmetric, but have different moduli, there is a mode II component which will cause the crack to grow into the more compliant material [6]. The moduli of the UD is much higher than the GMT and an asymmetric geometry with h_{GMT}/h_{UD} ratio of 2.5 was used to force the crack to grow into the UD adherend. The G_{Ic} values for the isothermal UD/UD bond were calculated as described in reference [3],

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\Delta}{2Ba}, \quad (3)$$

where P is the load, Δ is the crack opening displacement, and B is the specimen width.

RESULTS

The moduli of the GMT and UD plaques were calculated from the load-deflection curve and found to be 4.7 GPa and 31.7 GPa, respectively. The onset and peak melting temperatures of the GMT matrix were 151.9 and 164.7°C, respectively; the corresponding temperatures for the UD matrix were 149.7 and 167.0°C.

The G_{Ic} as a function of average temperature for the non-isothermal Series 1 bonds is shown in Figure 3a. The general trend is an almost linear dependence of G_{Ic} on average temperature. Crack propagation was always interfacial. Crack bridging was observed as the cracks grew, but was difficult to observe since Δ is only 0.45 mm. The G_{Ic} values for the lowest average temperature, 155°C, are between 2 and 4 kJ/m². At the highest average temperature, 180°C, the G_{Ic} values vary between 9 and 19 kJ/m². The G_{Ic} for the isothermal bond as a function of a is shown in Figure 3b. The G_{Ic} initiation value is approximately 2 kJ/m² at a crack length of 41 mm, and increases rapidly with crack length until a steady state propagation value of approximately 4.6 kJ/m² is reached. The transition from crack initiation to steady crack growth corresponded with the formation of fiber bridges during crack growth. Initially, there were no fiber bridges observed. However, as the crack grew, fiber bridging increased as did the measured G_I values. After approximately 10 mm of crack growth, the fiber bridging is fully developed and G_I reaches a steady state propagation value of 4.6 kJ/m².

The analysis of Series 2 bonds is more complicated since crack growth is not self-similar and not limited to a plane of fracture. Only for the lowest average temperature bonds did the cracks propagate along the interface. For the higher average temperature bonds, the cracks propagated across the interface in a series of parallel cracks inclined 20° to 30° away from the plane of the interface. The width of this interphase was usually less than 1 mm. Examining the assumptions underlying the derivation of Eqn (2), one finds that the cracks are, too short for the $h/a < 1$ assumption to be valid. Realizing that Eqn (2) does not give a true G_{Ic} for this complex multi-mechanism fracture process, it was chosen to compare specimens in this series which had been tested using two wedge thicknesses. The fracture energy as a function of average temperature for Series 2 is shown in Figure 4. The general trend in Figure 4 is similar to Series 1, but with considerably lower values; the fracture energy values for Series 2 bonds at 180°C are essentially the same as those for the highest values of the Series 1 bonds at 160°C. Fracture surfaces of the weakest and strongest bonds are compared in profile in Figure 5, where one can see the change from interfacial failure at low temperatures to cohesive failure at high temperatures. The crack also grows into the originally solid upper plaque. The DCB tests for the isothermal GMT/GMT bond did not result in any values for G_{Ic} . The beams were too compliant and failed in buckling close to the crack tip.

The bonds between the UD and the GMT were somewhat more difficult to compare. Unfortunately, the characterization of fracture energies for these bonds is not particularly useful due to the significant plastic deformation of the UD adherend for Series 3. In addition, the crack lengths for Series 3 and 4 were generally less than the thickness of the GMT adherend, which violates a key assumption of Eqn (2). However, there was no apparent plastic deformation of the adherends of Series 4 since all adherends were straight after fracture testing. Crack propagation for both series was always cohesive in the GMT. Comparing the average crack lengths as a function of the average temperature, shown in Figure 6, one can see that the crack lengths for Series 4 are approximately 1.7 mm longer than Series 3. In fact, for the solid UD/molten GMT bond at 154°C broke during preparation, indicating a very low fracture energy. In both cases there is a slight temperature dependence with the cracks becoming shorter at higher healing temperatures.

DISCUSSION

The general observation for all series was that increasing average temperature at the interface produced an increase in the fracture energy. The G_{Ic} values calculated for Series 1 by Eqn (2) were substantially higher than the propagation G_{Ic} value for the UD/UD DCB specimen. The reason for this difference could be explained by the nature of the bonding; isothermal for the DCB specimen and non-isothermal for Series 1. It was shown by Smith et al. [2] that non-isothermal bonding produced stronger bonds than isothermal bonding at low temperatures, but that these differences disappeared at average temperatures of 180°C. Since the DCB specimen was made at 200°C for 10 minutes, one would expect this bond to be as strong as the non-isothermal Series 1 bonds made at 180°C. The difference in G_{Ic} values may be explained by different stress states in the different specimen types. The width to thickness ratio for the DCB specimen is 10 and for the wedge test specimens is 8. Higher G_{Ic} -values would be expected for the wedge test specimens due to the lower degree of plane strain in these samples. This effect has been studied for carbon fiber/PEEK composites by Davies et al. [7], reporting that G_{Ic} values increased only 30% when decreasing the width to thickness ratio from 10 to 4. It would seem unlikely that the large differences in G_{Ic} values, approximately 200-400%, are due to differences in stress states alone. The DCB test is a direct measurement of the fracture process. The load is measured as a function of the displacement, and the calculated G_{Ic} reflects the work done during crack propagation. The wedge test is less direct. It measures the work done during crack propagation indirectly by calculating the work required to open the 2 beams of length a to displacement Δ . Mechanisms that dissipate energy are only detected if they lead to changes in a .

For the Series 2 bonds, the failure mode was interfacial at low temperatures with a transition at higher temperatures to cohesive failure. At higher temperatures, failure was always cohesive in the solid GMT plaque for Series 2, as shown in Figure 5. From the crack lengths of Series 3 and 4, bonding solid GMT to molten UD always produced a stronger bond than bonding solid UD to molten GMT. The failure mode for these series showed the same transition of Series 2, but the cohesive failure was always in the GMT. The 3-dimensional structure of the fibers in the GMT appears to deflect the crack away from the interface and into the bulk. This is an important result because it will control the sequence of processing operations for a multi-component structure. The characterization of the fracture energies between complex structures using more than one reinforcement geometry is difficult because the characterization of these structures by fracture mechanics is still not fully understood. Mode-mixity, reinforcement geometry, and a combination of fracture mechanisms, all play critical roles in characterizing these interfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The fracture energy of the of all 4 series increased with the average interface temperature. For the UD/UD bonds, the G_{Ic} values calculated from the non-isothermal wedge test were much higher than the propagation value from the isothermal DCB test. The calculated values of fracture energies for the GMT/GMT bonds was much lower than the fracture energies of the UD/UD bonds. The lowest average temperature for UD/UD bonds gave fracture energies approximately equal to the GMT/GMT bonds healed at the highest average temperature. Bonding between solid GMT and molten UD always produced higher fracture energy values than between molten GMT and solid UD. However, the bonds always failed in the GMT.

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Figure 1: The matched-die mold with facilities for separate heating and cooling of each mold half.

Figure 2: (a) the wedge test fracture geometry, (b) measurement of crack length using two 45° prisms on either side of the specimen.

Figure 3: (a) The critical strain energy release rate as measured by the wedge test for Series 1 bonds, the variation in G_{Ic} values at each point was typically 20%; (b) G_{Ic} as a function of crack length, or R-curve, for the UD/UD DCB bond.

Figure 4: The fracture energy as measured by the wedge test for Series 2 bonds. The variation in fracture energy values at each point was between 20% to 30%.

Figure 5: Profiles of the fracture surfaces (upper edges) of Series 2 bonds. *Top*, average temperature is 155°C; *bottom*, average temperature is 180°C.

Figure 6: The average crack length as a function of the average temperature for Series 3 and 4. The variation in crack length at each point was between 15% to 25%.